

UNIVERSITY JAUME

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In Spain, gender-based violence (GBV) has been addressed institutionally by higher education institutions (HEIs) for over a decade, fundamentally as a result of the obligations created in this regard by various national laws, such as Organic Act No 3/2007 on Effective Equality between Women and Men, Act No. 14/2011 on Science, Technology and Innovation, and Law 1/2004 Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence. Although this act does not make specific detailed reference to universities, it does raise the issue of education and awareness and establishes that both the State and the Autonomous Communities, within the scope of their respective powers, will adapt their regulations to the provisions contained in the Law. As a result, all Autonomous Communities have adopted their own laws against GBV. Only the Law 17/2020 of the Autonomous Community of Catalonia mentions specifically GBV in Universities.

In the past five years, however, the treatment of GBV has been marked by a surge in awareness of its structural rather than individual nature and has therefore seen the further adoption and/or renewal of institutional policies aimed at addressing GBV in an integrated manner through measures of prevention, detection, investigation, prosecution, partnership, protection, and service provision.

The most common instruments used to address GBV in HEIs (prescribed by law) are Institutional Equality Plans, which increasingly include GBV among their other equality aims, and dedicated Protocols, which address one or more forms of GBV.

Over the past five years there has also been a proliferation of other types of action to address GBV at the institutional level in HEIs. Examples are the creation of specialised units, the integration of GBV into university curricula and research, the development of awareness-raising and training, the publication of statements, and the creation of protection mechanisms, services, and partnerships designed to promote an equal and non-violent environment and prevent and combat GBV in HEIs. In addition, GBV has been increasingly addressed by umbrella organisations such as the Network of Gender Equality Units (RUIGEU) and the Conference of Rectors (CRUE), which have issued statements to show their commitment to the elimination of GBV in HEIs. A defining feature of all these is that they have widened their subjective and material scope beyond the earlier focus on women and sexual and sex-based harassment. There is now a focus on other vulnerable groups, especially gender and sexual minorities, through the increasing adoption of an intersectional perspective, and on other forms of GBV, most notably online forms of GBV and sexual violence.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University Jaume I (UJI) has two main policies that address GBV at the institutional level.

The first is the II Equality Plan of the UJI 2016-2020, which addresses violence, harassment, and discrimination on the grounds of gender, along with other equality aims. This plan has now expired and a new one is currently being drafted.

The second policy is the Protocol for Cases of Harassment at UJI, which was adopted in 2020.

URLs

- › II Equality Plan of the Universitat Jaume I 2016-2020: https://documents.uji.es/alfresco/d/d/workspace/SpacesStore/493b5035-4e5b-4632-902e-d23d0ca0eb87/II+PLAN+IGUALDAD_CAS+REVISADO.pdf?guest=true
- › Protocol for Cases of Harassment at UJI: <https://www.uji.es/serveis/ui/destacat/Protocol-antiassetjament/?urlRedirect=https://www.uji.es/serveis/ui/destacat/Protocol-antiassetjament/&url=/serveis/ui/destacat/Protocol-antiassetjament/>

Entry into force: The Equality Plan entered into force in 2016 and the Protocol in 2020.

TRAINING

The II Equality Plan of the UJI 2016-2020 includes various measures dedicated to the prevention of violence, which include trainings to promote equality and prevent violence offered throughout the university community and the introduction of a gender perspective in volunteer training.

The UJI also cultivates other activities to combat GBV. Worth mentioning is the creation of a permanent Purple-Rainbow Point on campus to offer information and advice on sexual harassment, GBV, and sexual and gender diversity. Its main objectives are to raise awareness, promote an inclusive and non-violent environment, offer attention to victims of violence, and prevent, combat, and eradicate all forms of discrimination. To this end, it offers training to the different groups that make up the university community, in particular as part of the Protocol. The university creates awareness-raising materials and campaigns; it also launched a Volunteer Group on gender equality and offers counselling to LBGQT people. Examples of the courses that have been offered include: the *Course for Managers and Directors on the Protocol*, which was designed to provide information about the Protocol's content and train people in management positions in the UJI to prevent and offer guidance on harassment; and a student course *Forms of Violence against Women*, which provided information on the types and modalities of GBV and on tools and strategies for its prevention.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

GBV is included in the curricula, especially in the master's related to gender equality. Knowledge on GBV is also occasionally produced via master theses on the topic.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies combined address the following **six** forms of GBV: physical violence, psychological violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, online violence, and another form (gender-based bullying).

Both policies address gender-based harassment. The Equality plan addresses physical violence, and the Protocol addresses psychological violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, and gender based bullying, including their online forms. The online forms cover a broad range of behaviours including gender-based online violence, online violence on the grounds of sex, sexual orientation, gender identity and expression, cyber-harassment, cyberbullying and sexting, when comprising the sending compromised or sexual images:

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harrassment | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harrassment | |

7Ps covered: Together the policies cover **6Ps** - prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and policies. Neither of the documents refers to partnership. The Equality plan does not cover prosecution and the provision of services, and the Protocol does not deal with prevalence.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

II Equality Plan of the Universitat Jaume I 2016-2020

Academic staff, non-academic staff, and students

Protocol for Cases of Harassment at UJI

Academic staff, non-academic staff, students and others

Both policies cover academic and non-academic staff as well as students. The Protocol for cases of harassment at UJI specifies that it applies to everyone who makes up the university community, that is, to administration and services staff (PAS), teaching and research staff (PDI), scholarship holders, students, and anyone who, even under the legal dependence of a third party, provides services within the scope of the Universitat Jaume I. It also applies to any person included in sections 1 and 2 whose relationship with Universitat Jaume I ended (under any legal form) due to a situation of harassment and who invoked this procedure within six months of the date on which the aforementioned relationship ended.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes. The Equality Plan focuses largely on gender while adopting a modest intersectional approach by proposing the inclusion within the Protocol of measures against psychological violence on the basis of sexual orientation and gender identity and expression.

The Protocol adopts a comprehensive intersectional approach, where it considers the need to create a space free from physical or mental violence against people and free from discrimination based on sex, age, nationality, racial or ethnic origin, sexual condition or orientation, functional diversity, marital status, religious beliefs, or any other personal or social circumstance. However, it only explicitly addresses gender identity and expression and sexual orientation in relation to harassment.

Specific vulnerable groups: LGBTQIA+ staff and students.

The Equality Plan mentions the need to promote an inclusive environment for reasons of sexual orientation, gender identity, and/or gender expression, and to prevent, combat, and eradicate any situation of discrimination in the university community for these reasons, as well as to include measures against psychological violence based on LGTBI sexual orientation in the university's protocol for detection, prevention, and action in cases of workplace harassment, sexual harassment, and harassment on the grounds of sex.

The Protocol mentions in general the need to create a space free from physical or mental violence against people and free from discrimination based on sex, age, nationality, racial or ethnic origin, sexual condition or orientation, functional diversity, marital status, religious beliefs or any other personal or social circumstance. However, it only explicitly addresses LGBT people, and only in relation to the creation of the UJI's permanent Purple-Rainbow Point on campus to offer information and advice on sexual harassment, GBV, and sexual and gender diversity.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Protocol mentions the general role of witnesses in the procedure as well as of those people accompanying victims but does not specify it further. It does, however, include these people in the measure regarding protection against intimidation, threats, or violence – against their person or their property – and against unfair or unfavourable treatment, persecution, discrimination, or retaliation of any kind. Any action in this sense will have disciplinary consequences in accordance with the applicable regulations and its investigation will also correspond to the CIRA.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Equality Plan addresses perpetrators in reference to violence, harassment, and discrimination on the grounds of gender in its proposal to consider the adoption of measures in relation to people convicted of GBV at UJI by the Vice-Rectorate for Academic Planning and Teaching Staff, Vice-Rectorate for Students, Employment and Educational Innovation, and the Vice-Rector for Economics and non-academic staff. Importantly, the Equality

Plan is the only document that addresses aggressors explicitly, even though it does not specify what such measures might be or how the decision to adopt them will be made.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The Equality Plan sets indicators relating to prevention:

- Objective 6.1. Establish procedures to prevent and manage harassment situations among members of the university community, which will be measured as the number of inquiries made on issues of violence, harassment, and discrimination based on gender.
- Objective 6.2. Fostering a culture of equality and non-violence in the UJI will be measured as the number of people in the UJI who have received training.

Monitoring: Yes. The Protocol establishes that the UJI will carry out the corresponding monitoring and evaluation in order not only to prevent the aforementioned behaviours, but also to influence the attitudes and behaviours of the people who make up the university community. While the Equality Plan included concrete aims, indicators, and evaluation procedures, the Protocol only foresees monitoring.

Evaluation: Yes. The Equality Plan stipulates that four years after the approval of the II Equality Plan, an external and independent evaluation must be made of it in order to determine the degree to which the actions have been implemented. An evaluation of the II Equality Plan of the UJI has been carried out by a person outside of the university who is an expert in equality policies. The results of the evaluation are available on the [UI website](#). The expert concluded that while the actions that the Equality Plan called for regarding GBV had been satisfactorily implemented (i.e. 48 people had solicited and received information on the matter in the five years of the plan's duration; the dedicated protocol had been updated and disseminated, and more than 10 training courses for staff and students had been developed in the same time period etc.), the only one not developed at all was that of measures relating to persons convicted of GBV.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. The Protocol sets out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigation applicable to all.

The Protocol defines: Who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, timeframe, responsible persons, outcomes, sanctions.

Who to contact: The Protocol establishes an institutional procedure for addressing concrete cases and provides for the creation of the Investigative Commission on Harassment Claims (CIRA), which, together with the Equality Unit, the Health and Safety Committee, and the General Secretariat, are the main actors responsible for both instruments.

How to report: The Protocol establishes that the following persons are authorised to present a claim or complaint: a member of the university community who a) feels they have been a victim of harassment, b) has knowledge of harassment having been perpetrated, with the express and written consent of the alleged victim, and c) trade union and student organisations with representation at the UJI, with the express and written consent of the alleged victim. The consent of the represented person can be revoked at any time during the procedure.

Time frame: Claims and complaints must be presented within a maximum period of three months of the date of the incident or incidents giving rise to the complaint, or, if it refers to persistent conduct, within three months of the last date on which the person was affected by said conduct. If a person wishes to invoke the procedure after this period has expired, a written request must be sent to the Equality Unit. In this writing, the circumstances that prevented a report of the incident being made within the prescribed period described above will be recorded. The Rectorate, in reference to the given circumstances, will decide whether the claim should be examined despite the delay.

Responsible persons: The Protocol establishes that an Investigative Commission on Harassment Claims (CIRA) will be set up for the purpose of the Protocol's implementation. Claims and complaints will be addressed to the Rectorate through any of the means provided in article 16 of Act No. 39/2015 of 1 October on the Common Administrative Procedure of Public Administrations. The rector will forward the claim to the CIRA within a maximum period of 5 business days to initiate steps in the investigation.

The investigation procedure: Once the claim or complaint has been transferred to the CIRA, CIRA will summon both parties separately to a preliminary exchange. With the result of these appearances, the possibility of a prior mediation within the 'Sindicatura de Agravios' (receivership of grievances) will be assessed. In this case, and with the agreement of the complainant, the CIRA will send the Sindicatura a copy of the minutes of the previous exchanges. The action of the Syndicate of Torts in this prior mediation process may not exceed 12 business days, counting from the day after the documentation delivered by the CIRA has been received. If the mediation process concludes with an agreement, the procedure will end and the CIRA will cease its actions. If it does not conclude with an agreement, the CIRA will take all the steps it deems appropriate to ensure an adequate technical assessment of the alleged facts and circumstances.

Outcome, sanctions: Within a maximum period of thirty business days from the beginning of its action, the CIRA will terminate the procedure and issue a written and reasoned report in which the absence or presence of signs of harassment is confirmed. The content of the report and the proposal will be subject to agreement by the members of the CIRA, who, where appropriate, may substantiate their votes/opinions. In the event that the CIRA decides that inappropriate behaviour such as isolated psychological violence has taken place, it will propose to the Rectorate the adoption of appropriate measures, both disciplinary and preventive. The CIRA will submit its final report to the Rector's Office and will inform the parties that said report has been delivered.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Lucrecia Rubio Grundell in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

